

STACKING SEQUENCE EFFECT ON POLYMER/COMPOSITE MULTI-LAYERS SUBMITTED TO THERMOMECHANICAL CYCLIC LOADINGS

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SUMMARY

Fast filling of a storage tank of hydrogen under pressure leads to thermomechanical stresses. Mechanical and thermomechanical cyclic tests have been performed on polymer/composite multi-layers and followed by using acoustic emission and microscopic observations. Results show the significant effect of composite stacking sequences and the influence of applied loading type.

Keywords: polymer/composite material, thermomechanical fatigue, stacking sequence, acoustic emission, damage development.

INTRODUCTION

This study is part of a work package of the “HYBOU” research program financially supported by the French Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR). This program is in the framework of the development of high-pressure hydrogen tanks (700 bars). The vessel structure considered here consists in a polymer liner and a filament wound composite shell made of carbon fibres and epoxy matrix. The polymer liner is required for the tightness of the tank, and the main function of the composite shell is to support stresses due to hydrogen pressure. Optimization of constituent materials is important in order to increase volumetric hydrogen density [1].

During the fast filling of a hydrogen storage tank, there is a simultaneous increase of two parameters. The pressure in the vessel increases, leading to an increase of stresses in the tank. At the same time, there is an increase of hydrogen temperature due to inverse Joule-Thompson effect and gas compression into the vessel. Studies [2-4] have shown the influences of initial mass and temperature of the gas, of the filling rate, and of constituent materials on such an increase of temperature. During the vessel life, numerous fast fillings are made, leading to a thermo-mechanical fatigue. Some studies have been performed on filament-wound composite pipes submitted to internal pressure and temperature gradient in order to optimize lay-up angles [5-6]. On the other hand, experimental works dealing with CFRP laminates behaviour have shown faster damage growth under thermal cycling than in mechanical fatigue [7]. Moreover, many authors

have shown the effectiveness of acoustic emission to characterise composite damage development (for example [8]).

The aim of this experimental study is to describe the behaviour of polymer/composite multi-layers submitted to thermo-mechanical cyclic loadings, close to those borne by the tank material during a fast filling. The composite part of the multilayer material has been made with different stacking sequences in order to study the influence of this geometric parameter on the damage development in thermo-mechanical fatigue. Indeed it is well known that, in CFRP laminates subjected to mechanical fatigue, thicker the transverse layers, faster the matrix cracking growth [9-11].

Moreover, in order to evaluate the specificity of the thermo-mechanical fatigue considered in this application, three types of loadings have been investigated and compared: quasi-static tensile tests, mechanical and thermo-mechanical cyclic tests.

MATERIALS

Studied polymer/composite multilayer materials correspond to constituent materials of “type IV” hydrogen vessel. The composite part of the multi-layer material is a carbon/epoxy pre-impregnated laminate. An 8 mm thick and 80 mm long polymer liner part is glued on the composite. Specimen geometry is shown in figure 1: 20 mm width, 130 mm of gauge length plus 50 mm length for gripping in each jaw of the testing machine.

The composite part presents two types of layers with different fibre orientations, noted respectively $A = (+\theta_1 / -\theta_1)$ and $B = (+\theta_2 / -\theta_2)$ where $15^\circ < \theta_1 < 35^\circ$ and $75^\circ < \theta_2 < 90^\circ$. Three different stacking sequences have been investigated: $[A_3B_2]_s$, $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and $[ABABA]_s$. They differ only by the thickness of A and B layers. Each sample has six A layers and four B layers, leading to a same 6 mm thickness of the composite part.

Figure 1: Tested samples geometry

As an example, the microscopic aspect of the polished edge of a $[ABABA]_s$ sample ‘as received’ is shown in figure 2. One can observe in this picture the different A and B layers and detect only few little defects.

Figure 2: Microscopic observation of the polished edge of a [ABABA]_s sample.

THERMOMECHANICAL FATIGUE TEST BENCH

In order to simulate the fast filling of hydrogen vessel under high pressure, a specific thermo-mechanical fatigue test bench has been specially developed (figure 3). It permits to control a simultaneous increase of pressure and temperature as occurring during the fast filling of a storage tank.

For the mechanical part of the test bench, a hydraulic fatigue machine INSTRON 1251 has been used to carry and control cyclic stresses in the specimen. Grips with manual tightening were used to fix samples in the machine, the clamping force being controlled by a torque wrench.

For the thermal part of the bench, an air stream is projected on the polymer liner part of the specimen, the applied temperature being controlled by a thermocouple placed very close to the specimen surface. A feedback between the mechanical and thermal parts of the bench ensures the synchronization, the thermal cycle being activated by a threshold value of the applied loading.

Figure 3: Experimental thermo-mechanical fatigue test bench

During tests, damage development has been characterized by acoustic emission (AE) and by microscopic observations of a polished lateral edge of the sample. Two sensors of AE were used to record acoustic activity as shown in figure 3.

QUASI-STATIC TENSILE TESTS

Quasi-static tensile tests with a constant crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/s have been performed on the multi-layers samples and compared according to the three different stacking sequences. Applied stresses have been calculated as the ratio of applied loads to composite cross-section area and global “strains” have been deduced from crosshead displacement measurements. The stress/strain curves obtained for the three studied laminates are shown in figure 4, where the stress values have been normalized relative to the failure stress of the $[ABABA]_s$ sample.

One can see in figure 4 that the three laminates present the same elastic linear behaviour for low stress levels. Then, the three curves deviate from linearity, and it can be seen that the thicker the layers, the earlier is this change in behaviour. During the tensile test performed on the $[ABABA]_s$ specimen, the first event of acoustic emission was detected precisely when the curve deviates from linearity: thus, such loss of linearity can be related to damage onset. Finally, the three laminates fail at different stress levels, and the comparison of the normalised failure stress values show that alternation of A and B layers is beneficial for the tensile resistance of the composite part of the multi-layer (figure 4).

Figure 4: Normalized stress vs. strain curves of quasi-static tensile tests up to failure performed on the multilayer samples with three stacking sequences.

MECHANICAL AND THERMO-MECHANICAL FATIGUE TEST

Different types of fatigue loadings have been investigated and the response of the different stacking sequences have been compared.

First, mechanical fatigue tests have been carried out with a test frequency of 1Hz. As shown in figure 5a, triangular stress cycles with a one second period were applied, with a stress varying from 0MPa to $46\% \sigma_{r[ABABA]_s}$, noted σ_{fat} . σ_{fat} corresponds to a stress level for which the quasi-static tensile test curve for $[ABABA]_s$ is still linear and is non-linear for $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and $[A_3B_2]_s$ (figure 4). The second type of tests consisted in applying nine minutes long trapezoidal stress cycles presenting a Constant Stress Level (CSL) stage (figure 5b). The stress is increasing during two minutes, corresponding to the fast filling

of the vessel, and then the maximum stress is maintained for six minutes. Comparison between those two types of fatigue tests permits to investigate the influence of time on the multilayer fatigue behaviour. Finally, thermo-mechanical tests have been performed: the same trapezoidal stress cycles than in mechanical fatigue with CSL were applied and simultaneously, a temperature cycle corresponding to the gas temperature increase during fast filling, followed by a controlled cooling back to initial temperature (figure 5c). Comparison between thermo-mechanical fatigue and mechanical fatigue with CSL allows putting in light the effect of temperature on the fatigue behaviour of the multilayer.

Figure 5: The different types of fatigue tests: (a) 1 Hz mechanical cycle (b) mechanical cycle with CSL (c) thermo-mechanical cycle.

Damage Observations

Several microscopic observations of the specimen edges have been achieved during the different fatigue tests. During 1 Hz mechanical fatigue tests, microscopic observations have been realized after 400 cycles on $[A_3B_2]_s$ and $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and after 15,000 cycles on $[ABABA]_s$. Damage has always been observed in single layer B. In $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and $[ABABA]_s$ stacking sequences, it consists in matrix cracks which cross B layer thickness. Figure 6b shows that matrix cracks are accompanied by fibre/matrix debonding. More numerous cracks have been observed in $[A_2B_2A]_s$ than in $[ABABA]_s$. For the multilayer with $[A_3B_2]_s$ stacking sequence, with only one central B layer, the observed damage is quite different: the thick B layer seems to be “divided in several blocks” due to branching of matrix cracks, delamination inside the B layer and delamination between A and B layers (figure 6c).

During mechanical fatigue tests with CSL stage, microscopic observations have been realized after 100 and 200 cycles on $[A_3B_2]_s$ and $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and also after 400 cycles on $[A_2B_2A]_s$. Same types of damage than in 1 Hz mechanical cycling have been observed and still in single B layers. In $[A_2B_2A]_s$, for example, the crack number increases with the cycle number: respectively 33, 46, 57 cracks after 100, 200 and 400 cycles, and in the same time, crack opening is growing (respectively $8\mu\text{m}$, $9\mu\text{m}$ and $11\mu\text{m}$ for a given crack). Delamination between A and B layers that initiates at matrix crack end has also been noticed after 400 cycles (figure 6a). In multilayer sample with $[A_3B_2]_s$ stacking sequence, it has been remarked that central B layer is divided in smaller blocks after 200

cycles than after 100 cycles. And the opening of delamination between A and B layers increases with the number of cycles (respectively 65 μ m and 100 μ m for a given delamination after 100 and 200 cycles).

During thermo-mechanical fatigue test, microscopic observations have been achieved during the first cycle on $[A_3B_2]_s$ and after 400 cycles on $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and $[ABABA]_s$. Same types of damage as for mechanical fatigue tests are present, always in B layers, but in very small number in $[ABABA]_s$. In $[A_2B_2A]_s$, for the same cycle number, cracks are more opened than in mechanical fatigue with CSL stage. For example, after 400 cycles, crack opening is approximately 20 μ m large in thermo-mechanical fatigue compared to about 10 μ m in mechanical fatigue with CSL. Moreover, a large wide opened delamination between A and B layers (with an opening of 150 μ m) has been observed under the glued liner polymer in the $[A_2B_2A]_s$ composite part after 400 cycles. In $[A_3B_2]_s$, the thick central B layer is found “divided into several blocks” from the first cycle: that shows that in thermo-mechanical fatigue, the damage development rate is far higher in this stacking sequence.

These results show a significant effect of stacking sequence on damage development: thicker B layers, faster damage growth. Moreover, thermo-mechanical cycling leads to faster damage increase than mechanical cycling, that puts in light the influence of temperature on multilayer fatigue behaviour. And, mechanical cycling with CSL stage leads to faster damage development than 1 Hz mechanical cycling, showing a significant role of the duration of the cycles on the material fatigue behaviour.

Figure 6: (a) $[A_2B_2A]_s$: matrix cracking in B layer and delamination between A and B layers observed after 400 cycles of mechanical fatigue with CSL stage (b) $[ABABA]_s$: matrix cracking and fibre/matrix interface debonding observed in B layer after 15000 cycles of 1 Hz mechanical fatigue (c) $[A_3B_2]_s$: B layers “divided in blocks” observed after one cycle of thermo-mechanical fatigue.

Damage Development by Acoustic Emission

Fatigue tests have also been followed by AE. Detected events are hits occurred between the two sensors in the listening zone (figure 3). In figures 7 and 8 are presented cumulated event numbers measured during the first 400 cycles according to the different stacking sequences and the different types of fatigue tests.

Whatever the applied fatigue type, figure 7 shows that there is no AE activity during the first 100 cycles for $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and $[ABABA]_s$ composite stacking sequences. On the opposite, for multilayer samples with $[A_3B_2]_s$ stacking sequence, AE events were always detected from the first loading cycle. Then, whatever the applied fatigue loading type, AE event number increases more rapidly in $[A_3B_2]_s$ than in $[A_2B_2A]_s$, which increases more rapidly than in $[ABABA]_s$. For example, in 1 Hz mechanical fatigue tests, after 400 cycles, 712 AE events were detected in $[A_3B_2]_s$, 120 in $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and no one in $[ABABA]_s$ (figure 7a).

These results are in accordance with microscopic observations, showing a significant effect of stacking sequence on damage growth. For every type of loading, alternation of different orientation composite layers is beneficial to damage resistance of the laminate.

Figure 7: Cumulative AE events detected during tests, (a) 1 Hz mechanical fatigue, (b) mechanical fatigue with CSL stage (c) thermo-mechanical fatigue loading

Figure 8: Cumulated AE events detected during fatigue tests

(a) $[A_3B_2]_s$, (b) $[A_2B_2A]_s$ and (c) $[ABABA]_s$.

On the other hand, whatever the composite stacking sequence, comparison of AE results according to the different types of fatigue loadings shows that temperature cycling and low frequencies have a harmful effect on damage development (figure 8). For example, for $[A_2B_2A]_s$, after 400 cycles, 120 AE events were detected for the 1 Hz mechanical fatigue loading, 232 for the mechanical fatigue with CSL stage and 360 for the thermo-mechanical fatigue test (figure 8b).

Fatigue Life

Normalized values of number of fatigue cycles at failure are given in table 1, according to the different stacking sequences and the different types of loading considered. These values have been calculated as the ratios of the number of cycles at failure to the one obtained for the $[ABABA]_s$ multilayer in a 1 Hz mechanical fatigue test. Results show that for each type of fatigue, fatigue life is higher for $[ABABA]_s$ than for $[A_2B_2A]_s$, which is higher than for $[A_3B_2]_s$. As expected after damage observations, the alternation of different orientation layers leads to higher fatigue life of the laminate.

Results in table 1 also confirm previous observations: coupling temperature cycling with mechanical cycling or decreasing cycle frequency leads to shorter fatigue life of these multi-materials.

Table 1: Normalized fatigue life according to the three stacking sequences and the three types of fatigue loading

	$[A_3B_2]_s$	$[A_2B_2A]_s$	$[ABABA]_s$
1 Hz mechanical fatigue	17.2%	55.8%	100%
Mechanical fatigue with CSL stage	1.19%	>1.31%	No test
Thermomechanical fatigue	0.27%	0.41%	>1.44%

CONCLUSION

This experimental study has shown that there is a significant effect of composite stacking sequence on multilayer behaviour whatever the loading type. AE activity, microscopic observations and failure characteristics show that alternation of different orientation layers in composite part is beneficial for the multilayer fatigue life.

Moreover, results exhibited the influence of the loading cycle duration and of a stress upholding on the damage growth and fatigue life, that could be associated with the viscous behaviour of composite matrix.

And, comparison between different fatigue tests have put in light the harmful role of coupled temperature/mechanical cycling on the multilayer fatigue behaviour.

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